

THE SYSTEM OF SERVICE AUTOMATION STRUCTURE IN SERVICE SPHERES

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ABSTRACT

One of the features of the service market is high competition. In such an environment, it is important for the organization to increase business profitability, optimize accounting and management. The speed of solving these problems directly depends on the efficiency of the automation system.

The modern approach to automating this service sector involves the creation of a project management system. Human resource management and customer relationship management are key components of the project portfolio. In fact, they reflect two sides of the same coin, because the success of an enterprise depends on the customers, and the quality of the services to which the customers refer depends on the social and psychological skills of the employees.

The project direction combines business processes such as time management, accounting, evaluation of project financial performance, and analytical information retrieval. However, you can monitor the progress of the project using visual reports that include step-by-step evaluations, analytical data, and objectives of the work.

The schematic diagram of automation is the main technical document of the project, which shows the level and principle of automation of the technological device. This reflects all the key decisions made at the initial stage of building a management system. The drawing should provide an understanding of the control object, the tools used in control, adjustment, program control, signaling, interlocking, protection, and automation. Usually alarm, blocking and protection are extended in special drawings. The schematic diagrams, along with the controls and communications, show a diagram of the technological devices, automation tools, schematic diagrams of the interactions between the various devices of the technological units and the automation tools.

Due to a number of issues related to production automation, specialists in various fields have the opportunity to bring their products, programs or developments to the European market. The business program implemented within the thematic project will help to deepen the essence of problematic and innovative issues. In a rapidly evolving technological environment, enterprises need new solutions, including: increasing product volumes; perform labor-intensive technical tasks in a short time; reducing the cost of raw materials and waste; doing things that cannot be achieved by human hands; only innovative systems such as production automation, ie. transfer of management and control functions from human to technical equipment.

The main role of the introduction of automation systems is to increase efficiency, mobility and simplify the work of staff. As a result of these changes, the level of competitiveness in the market is increasing and the strong use of the resource base continues. Production automation can be done in several ways, in particular: Only certain equipment is automated, which performs a series of actions that people cannot or cannot achieve. Covers the production chain of a particular shop or unit that performs a series of actions to solve a specific problem. Management and control is being transferred to special equipment that covers all stages of production. This occurs in a stable and practical mode, as well as in situations where working conditions are extremely dangerous or unbearable for the worker. To better determine the level of automation, you need to know its effectiveness for a particular type of

production. Automation has been created by technologists to make working conditions as comfortable as possible for people and to improve the operation of the equipment and make it easier to operate.

Today, this system is implementing itself in various directions, for example: Production automation has been created to improve the internal labor system. For example, a more equipped machine or training system that allows you to work on a large scale of production is designed to work with technologies that allow you to expand your knowledge capabilities and make it easier to learn new programs. Automation covers the areas of design, planning and management. He runs the business processes. The technical support system helps to increase labor productivity, improve product quality. Automation by eliminating manual labor In addition to the benefits listed, it also aims to protect the human body. Thus, for example, there are enterprises that produce tobacco or aluminum, which is contraindicated for humans. The automation of production ensures the complete elimination of human labor, its replacement by specialized machines. Automation is also used in service areas, such as cafes and restaurants, shops, supermarkets, and more. The structure of the processes that take place in such institutions is crucial.

The presence of barcodes - they help to mark and correct the goods, and thus immediately provide information about the arrival of products in the database. Barcode Scanner - Provides information on whether a product is available. Each unit is knocked out under a specific code, which allows you to track its

quantity at the time of receipt and completion of the sale of the product.

Thanks to the latest developments, many employees can not only get the appropriate working conditions, but also the opportunity for retraining, which in turn will ensure the growth of the company and the development of employees.

Today, a number of facilities are provided in the field of services for the population to live in a comfortable and comfortable environment. As a result, due to the development of service infrastructure in rural areas of the country, the lifestyle of the rural population is approaching the lifestyle of the urban population. In order to develop the industry in accordance with modern requirements, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan signed a decree "On the program of development of the service sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2012-2016" and "On the provision of services in rural areas in 2013-2016." On Additional Measures to Accelerate the

Development of the Supply and Service Sector ". As a result of programs and measures aimed at developing the service sector, the share of the industry in GDP has grown significantly. The figure is expected to be 54.5% today, up from 50.5% in 2011. People employed in the industry today make up more than 50% of the total employed population.

Today, 80.4 thousand or 81% of small businesses operate in the service sector. More than 2,000 companies operating in the industry across the country are benefiting from the program. Due to the implementation of the program, the total volume of services increased by 1.7 times, and services per capita - by 1.6 times. It is no exaggeration to say that the main high rates of development in the industry are in finance, construction, healthcare, communications and information, computer programming, maintenance and repair of agricultural machinery, and household services.

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